

THE STATUS OF STREET CHILDREN IN SOME COSMOPOLITAN CENTRES IN ONDO STATE

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ABSTRACT

The status of street children in Ondo State was evaluated in Ondo West and Akure Local Government Areas. Two major towns (Ondo and Akure) were used for the selection of samples. One hundred and eighteen children were used for the study in some cosmopolitan centres viz: Ife Garage, Sabo and Igele in Ondo and under the bridge, around the mosque and around the major market in Akure. It was discovered that 67.9% of the children interviewed went to school and were still in school while 32.1% were not in school. The average age was thirteen years for the two groups of children interviewed. Most of the children who did not go to school hawked various commodities to have money – to help their parents, to feed, to meet up with colleagues, to obtain freedom from apprenticeship etc (77.8%, 90.5%, 75% and 100% in Ife Garage, Sabo, Igele and Akure respectively). The highest money earned among those who did not go to school (between ₦40.00 and ₦400.00) per day was made at Sabo. It was not determined whether this was net gain or total sales. Many of the children responded that they would stop selling if someone sponsored their education or if they were allowed to live with someone who would take care of them and send them to school. Most of the children have been on the streets for five years and below. All the children hawked common goods and food items on the streets and markets. Many of those who were not in school wished to go back to school, learn a trade or go to school, then finally learn a trade.

INTRODUCTION

It has been observed that many children are found in the street. Some just wander about without any particular destination in mind. Some are seen hawking one type of ware or the other while others relish in staying away from home and remain outside. These categories of children are here described as street children.

Street children can be found in rural areas as well as in big cities. In the rural communities, they engage in selling various commodities, especially food items, which are very useful for breakfast. In later morning and afternoon, they either go to

school or farm and so the streets are "deserted". They are however seen in the evenings again selling and running around until evening time when they are forced by darkness to retire home.

The children are quite different in the cities, which are commercial centres. Large numbers of children are seen on the streets carrying out all sorts of activities. Some stay in bus stops hawking their wares while others go about in the streets. Some of these children stay relatively permanently in motor parks. There is hardly any time of the day that the street children are not noticeable in the cities. The case of Lagos Hausas concentrate in a city often called "Sabo" seems different. Street children are often seen begging for alms from passers-by.

This characteristic of street children is very common in the cities located in the Northern part of Nigeria. Many able-bodied children can be seen picking food from dustbins. They are also found in and around local restaurants, known as "Mama Alimosho" trying to pack and consume the remnants of food eaten by customers.

The street children engage in one type of work or the other, including begging. Remington (1993) reported that the actual numbers of street and working children in India stood at 44 million. Bond (1994) gave 30 million as the estimate of street children or vagabonds in the world. An estimate of the actual number of street children in Nigeria does not seem to be readily available.

This study was carried out to find out the status of street children in Ondo State. A study is necessary to find out:

- i. the reasons why children roam the streets and what can be done to reduce and eradicate the incidence;
- ii. the percentage of those on the street who were in school before;
- iii. the reason why they left school;
- iv. the percentage of those on the street who are still in school;
- v. the reasons why they are on the street;
- vi. the percentage of those on the street who are hawkers;
- vii. the percentage of those on the street who are beggars;
- viii. the percentage of those on the street who are guides to beggars;
- ix. what plans the street children have for their future;
- x. if they want to continue as beggars/hawkers;
- xi. what they think can be done to stop their being on the street;
- xii. if their parents know that they are on the street; and
- xiii. what they do with the money they make from hawking/begging.

The study will help

- (i) the government to know why children roam the streets and how she can reduce or eradicate it;
- (ii) the parents and government to know what can send children to the street.
- (iii) the government to know how to prevent other children from joining those presently on the street
- (iv) the government to make a plan for those presently on the street.

This work sought to answer the following questions:

- (i) Why are children on the street?
- (ii) What are they doing on the street?
- (iii) What is the percentage of those on the street who were in school before?
- (iv) Why did they leave?
- (v) What is their plan for the future?
- (vi) Does family background have an effect on children roaming the street?
- (vii) How much money (on the average) do street children make a day begging/hawking?
- (viii) How do they spend the money?
- (ix) Do they want to continue begging/hawking?
- (x) What do they think can be done to stop their being on the street?
- (xi) Do majority of parents of street children support their being on the street?
- (xii) Is poor performance in the school one of the factors that force children to the street?

Research Methodology

Population and Sample

This study was carried out in Ondo West and Akure Local Government Areas of Ondo State. Two major towns (Ondo and Akure) were used for the selection of samples. One hundred and eighteen (118) children were used for the study (60 from Ondo and 58 from Akure). They were randomly selected from a motor park (Ife Garage), Sabo (where Hausas are the predominant inhabitants) and the major market (Igele) all in Ondo town. They were also from under the bridge, around the central mosque and around the major market (Oja Oba) in Akure town. The age of the children ranged from six to eighteen years (6 to 18 years).

Below is a table (Table 1) showing the places where the interview was conducted and the town where such places are found.

Table 1: Location of the Street Children

Serial No	Town	No	Place where the interview was conducted
1	Ondo	1	Ife Garage
		2	Sabo
		3	Igele
2	Akure	1	Under the bridge
		2	Around the central mosque
		3	Around the major market

The Instrument

The instrument used was a questionnaire/interview schedule for street children. The questionnaire was made up of two parts. Part A consisted of background information about the street children as appropriate. It consisted of ten (10) questions which had to do with the family background of the street children including age, the level of education of their parents, the type of family (monogamous or polygamous) they came from. Part B consisted of fifteen (15) questions designed to provide answers to the research questions. The fifteen questions included questions on whether their parents know that they were hawking/begging, why they were hawking/begging, if they were in school before, their performance while in school, if they were in school, what class they were when they left school, their plan for the future, how much they earned a day begging/hawking, if they wanted to continue as beggars/hawkers, how long they had been on the street. The questionnaire was an open-ended type.

Validation of the Instrument

The draft the questionnaire was given to three experts in the field of education and one in psychology. The draft was modified in line with the comments of these experts and the final instrument was produced and administered to the respondents.

Procedure for the Administration of the Instrument

The questionnaire was filled for all the respondents. A Hausa interpreter was used to translate the questions to Hausa to respondents who could communicate only in Hausa language. The response was translated to the researcher by the interpreter in English or Yoruba. The responses of some respondents were tape-recorded to save time. The writing of the responses took some time and some of the respondents felt bored or saw it as a waste of time hence the need for the tape recorder.

Below is Table 2 showing the number of boys and girls and the places where they were interviewed.

Table 2: Number of boys and girls and the places where they were interviewed

Serial No	Place where interview took place	No. of boys	No of girls	Total no of children
1-9	Ife Garage	1	8	9
10-41	Sabo	19	12	32
42-60	Igele	8	11	19
1-27	Under the Bridge	18	9	27
28-39	Around the mosque	6	6	12
40-58	Around the market	10	9	19
	Total	62	56	118
	Percentage	52.5%	47.5%	

RESULTS

Table 3: Background Information of Street Children Who Do Not Go To School

	Ife Garage, Ondo (n = 9)	Sabo, Ondo	Igele, Ondo (n = 4)	Akure (n = 4)
Age Range	10-20	6-16	6-16	5-15
Average Age	15	1	12	12
Sex	Male -1 Female - 8	Male -11 Female -10	Male -2 Female - 2	Male -3 Female -1
Fathers Occupation	Soldier, Carpenter, Teaching, Driving, Bricklaying, Farming	Trading, Farming, Driving, no occupation	Bank Worker, Soldier, Driving, Trading	Driving, Furniture, Has someone who drives for him
Mother's Occupation	Trading, Nursing, Sewing Teaching	Fashion designing, Trading Housewife, no occupation, Hair- dressing, Sewing	Hair- Dressing, Trading	Trading, Hair- dressing
No of Father's wives	One; 4 Two;5	One; 12 Two; 5 Three; 4	One; 3 Two;1	One; 1 Two ; 1 Three; 1 Twelve; 1
Position in Fathers children	2 nd : 1 5 th : 2 6 th : 1	1 st : 7 2 nd :1 3 rd : 6 4 th : 4 5 th : 1 10 th :1 11 th : 1	2 nd :2 4 th : 1 6 th : 1	1 st : 1 3 rd : 1 4 th : 1 13 th : 1

4	Plan for the future	Go back to school if there is money - 4 Learn a trade - 2 Civil service - 1 Trading - 1	Join the army - 2 Teaching - 1 Get married - 7 Hairdressing - 2 Fashion designing - 1 Trading - 6 Medical doctor - 1 Doesn't know - 1	Became Rev Sister - 1 Will learn a trade - 1 Will learn a trade or sell - 1 Sell meat - 1	Wants to go to school - 1 Learn a trade - 1 Wants to go to school, then learn a trade - 1 Become a nurse - 1
		Ife Garage (n=9)	Sabo, Ondo (n=21)	Igele, Ondo (n=4)	Akure (n=4)
5	Money earned a day	Sells for master/takes money home - 2 Net gain - N80 - N100 - 2 Net gain N150 - 1 N20 N40 - 1; N200 - 2	N40 - N100 - 9 N110 - N200 - 7 N300 - N400 - 1 N20 - N200 - 2	N10.00 or N20.00 - 1 N80.00 - 1 Net gain N50 - 1 Net gain N60 - 1	Net gain Net gain N15 - N50 - 1 Total Sales N40 - 1 N200 - 1
6	How the money is spent	Save the money/save it with her mother - 2 To buy food - 6	Save it - 4 Given to guardian/parent/mother - 11 To buy things for himself/clothes/feeding - 3, save give some to guardian and some or rest on food - 2	Save it - 3 Gives to parents - 1	To feed - 1 Gives to guardian - 2 Saves it (contribution) - 1

7	Wants to continue begging or not	Yes = 5; No = 4	Yes = 11; No = 0	Yes = 4; No = 0	Yes = 3; No = 1
8	How long have they been on the street	Less than 1 year = 4 1 - 3 years = 4 7 years = 1	Less than 1 year = 2 1- 5 years = 16 6- 8 years = 3	Less than one month - 1 One month = 1 5 years = 1 6 years = 1	Less than 1 year = 1 About 1 year = 1 4 to 5 years = 2
9	What can be done to stop their being on the street	Nothing = 2 Nothing (doesn't know) = 1 If she gets money for hairdressing/freedom = 2 If she gets money/someone gives her money to go back to school = 2 If he is given money = 1	Nothing = 5 If he is sent to school = 9 Getting married = 4 When he is rich = 1 If there is money to learn fashion designing = 1 If he has money to go back to Abia State = 1	Nothing = 1 If he is asked to learn a trade = 1 If she is sponsored to school or given money - 1 When she becomes a Rev. Sister = 1	If she is allowed to give someone who will take care of her and send her to school = 2 If given plenty of money = 1

4	Plan for the	Go back to school if there is	Join the army - 2 Teaching - 1	Became Rev Sister - 1 Will learn a trade - 1	Wants to go to school - 1
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Table 4 shows that majority of the parents of street children who hawked and did not go to school knew that their children hawked (100%, 100%, 75% and 75% in Ife Garage, Sabo, Igele and Akure respectively).

Most of the children hawked so as to have money for various reasons, mostly to help parents, to feed, to meet up with colleagues, to obtain freedom from apprenticeship etc. (77.8%, 90.5%, 75% and 100% in Ife Garage, Sabo, Igele and Akure respectively).

All the children hawked one thing or the other on the street (100% for all children interviewed) e.g. iced water, meat, bread, doughnut, nylon bags, cooked rice, chinchin, etc. Some sell Tuwo (a Hausa diet) at Sabo, Ondo.

At the Garage, 44.4% of the children wanted to go back to school if there was money, 33.3% of them wanted to learn a trade while 11.1% of them wanted to join the civil service when they grew up. At Sabo, however, 85.7% of them wanted to get married or join the army, trade or learn hairdressing and fashion designing. At Igele also in Ondo 75% of them wanted to learn a trade or sell. At Akure 50% wanted to learn a trade or go to school then finally learn a trade. 25% wanted to go to school and 25% wanted to become nurses.

At the Garage, 77.8% made between ₦80.00 and ₦200.00 a day. Only 22.2% sold for their masters or took the money home. 81% at Sabo made between ₦40.00 and ₦400.00 a day. Only 4.8% (at Sabo) claimed that they made up to ₦1,400.00 a day. At Igele 100% (all the children) made between ₦10.00 and ₦80.00 a day. At Akure 75% made between ₦15.00 and ₦50.00 while 25% made ₦200.00 a day.

Of the children interviewed at Ife Garage, 22.2% saved the money and 66.7% spent the money on food. At Sabo 71.4% either saved the money themselves to give it to their guardians or parents or mothers. 14.3% spent the money on clothes and feeding. At Igele 100% saved it or gave it to parents. At Akure, 75% saved it or gave to their guardian while 25% spent it on feeding.

At Ife Garage 55.6% wanted to continue hawking while 44.4% did not. At Sabo 52.7% wanted to continue while 47.3% did not. At Igele all (100%) wanted to continue hawking. At Akure 75% wanted to continue while 25% did not.

88.9% of the children at Ife Garage had been on the street for three years or less while 21.1% had been there for seven years. 85.7% at Sabo had been on the street for five years or less while 24.3% had been there for six to eight years. At Igele 75% had been on the street for five years or less and the remaining 25% had been there for six years. At Akure all (100%) had been on the street for five years or less.

At Ife Garage 55.6% of the children interviewed were of the opinion that if they got money to learn a trade (hairdressing) or to go back to school, they would leave the streets. At Sabo 52.3% responded that if they were sent to

school or if they got money to learn a trade (fashion designing) or go back to their home-towns, they would leave the streets. At Igele 50% of the children would leave the streets if they were asked to learn a trade or if sponsored to school or given money. At Akure 75% would leave the streets if they were allowed to live with someone who would take care of them and send them to school or if they were sent to school. Few of the children (33.3%, 23.8% and 25% at Ife Garage, Sabo and Igele respectively) said that nothing could be done to stop their being on the street.

DISCUSSION

The results of this study show that the average age of street children who do not go to school was thirteen years. This agrees with the report of Okwaraji *et al* (1996) who studied street children in Enugu metropolis. He found that the average age of the street children involved was thirteen years. Balamir (1982) also reported that in Turkey, about 57,000 children aged 12-14 worked in manufacturing industries.

Most of the children in this study hawked to help their parents to feed, to meet up with colleagues etc. (77.8%, 90.5%, 75% and 100% in Ife Garage, Sabo, Igele and Akure respectively refer to Table 3). This supports Balamir (1982) and Pitt and Shah (1982) who respectively reported that working children add to the family income, that they are a kind of pension plan looked up to for support during old age and that child labour is a form of participation, a way in which children can share in redistribution of wealth through earning wages.

Very few of the children occupied the first position among their father's children (refer to Tables 1 and 2). This supports Sawhney (1979) who said that children who live in large families are more likely to be poorer than those who live in small families. Nigam (1994) was also of the opinion that children are on the streets due to poverty and their parents' unemployment.

In all the children studied, there were more males than females at Sabo in Ondo and Akure (52.4% and 75% respectively). This is the same as what Kulkarni (1979) found out that in rural areas of India among children aged 5-14, only 11.78% of the males and 4.78% of the females engaged in work.

As could be seen from Tables 1 and 2 most of the fathers had one wife (80%, 57.1% and 75% at Ife Garage, Sabo and Igele respectively). This is far from what one would expect. One would have expected that having more than one wife would be one of the factors that could force children on the streets.

From the study it can be seen that the highest number of those who did not go to school was found at Ife Garage (100%) followed by 65.6% at Sabo.

The fathers were soldiers, carpenters, teachers, drivers, bricklayers, farmers, traders and bank workers. The mothers were teachers, traders, hairdressers, tailors, farmers, civil servants, nurses, housewives and without occupation.

Most of the parents were aware that their children hawked on the streets (100%, 100%, 75% and 75% in Ife Garage, Sabo, Igele and Akure respectively). This shows that the children hawked mostly with the consent of their parents.

77.8% of the children at Ife Garage made between ₦80.00 and ₦200.00 a day, 81% at Sabo made between ₦40.00 and ₦400.00. 100% made between ₦10.00 and ₦80.00 at Igele. At Akure 75% made between ₦15.00 and ₦50.00. The highest amount earned was at Sabo. Another study is needed to determine whether this was their net gain or total sales

55.6%, 52.7%, 100% and 75% in Ife Garage, Sabo, Igele and Akure respectively wanted to continue hawking

88.9% of the children at Ife Garage had been on the street for 3 years or less. At Sabo and Igele, 85.7% and 75% respectively had been on the street for 5 years or less. This shows that most of the children have been on the streets for five years and less.

55.6% at Ife Garage, 52.3% at Sabo and 50% at Igele responded that if they were sent to school or earned money to learn a trade they would leave the streets. At Akure 75% would leave the streets if they were allowed to live with someone who would take care of them and send them to school or if they were sent to school. From this we can see that many of the children did not want to stay on the streets. They preferred going to school if they had the means. They seemed to be hawking to help their parents to make ends meet. This agrees with the report of Prince Egede (Labour Reporter) in the *Guardian Newspaper* of Thursday, April 16, 1998. He reported that poverty had been cited as one of the fundamental causes of the growing trend of child labour in the world especially in sub-Saharan Africa, and that about 800 million children were currently engaged in one form of child labour or the other in the continent. According to him, delegates from 22 African countries including Nigeria at a three-day International Labour Organization meeting on "Child Labour in Africa" recently held in Kampala, Uganda, called for increase international assistance to attack widespread poverty currently ravishing the continent. In the final report of the conference, attention was drawn to the alarming increase of child labourers and it was recommended that universal primary education must be provided as one of the necessary preventive measures. It added that keeping children in school now is the most important measure. The conference agreed that in the light of the social and economic situation prevailing Africa, some of the children might be required to work in the medium and short term. But the work should be regulated and should not endanger the health and safety of the child and should combine protected work activities with some kind of education and social services.

At Ife Garage 44% of the children wanted to go back to school if there were money, 50% at Akure wanted to learn a trade or go to school and the same percentage in the same place wanted to become nurses. From the above it can be said that many of those who were not in school still wanted to go to school if they had the opportunity. 11.1% at Ife Garage also wanted to join the civil service when they grow up while 85.7% at Sabo wanted to get married or join the army, trade or learn hairdressing and fashion designing.

The study revealed that children were mostly on the street hawking common food items, snacks and fruits e.g. cooked rice, meat, bread, yam fried plantain, vegetables, doughnut, chinchin, mangoes, okra, kolanut, tuwo, masa and fura (The last four items were sold at Sabo only).

No child was seen begging or leading a beggar in this study. This shows that this practice is fast fading out in this part of the country.

Most of the children who were not in school hawked to help parents, to feed, to meet up with colleagues to obtain freedom from apprenticeship etc.

Among those who did not go to school the highest money earned daily (N40.00 to N400.00) was made at Sabo.

Many of the children wanted to continue hawking (at Igele all the children who were not in school wanted to continue hawking). Most of the children have been on the street for five years and less.

Many of the children responded that they would stop selling if someone sponsored their education or if they were allowed to live with someone who would take care of them and send them to school. They preferred going to school if they had the means. They seemed to be hawking to help their parents to make ends meet.

Some of the children had plans (even specific professions e.g. mobile policemen, soldiers, medical doctors, nurses, lawyers, engineering, accountancy etc) for their future. Many of those who were not in school wished to go to school if they had the opportunity. Only at Sabo many of them wanted to get married or learn a trade in future. Majority of their parents knew that they were hawking.

Most of the children who did not go to school saved the money earned themselves or gave it to their parents or guardians.

There were more boys than girls on the street (52.2% of those interviewee were boys and 47.5% were girls). In most of the places where the interview took place there were more boys than girls.

Conclusion

Poverty is the fundamental cause of children hawking on the streets. Children wish to go to school or learn a trade and become important people in future but they hawk as a result of the poor economic situation in the country.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study and the analysis made in the above discussions, it is hereby strongly recommended that:

1. There should be increased international assistance to attack widespread poverty currently ravishing the country.
2. There should be universal primary and secondary education so as to keep children in school. Their education is very important, even before somebody learns a trade he should have at least JSS3 certificate. It will enable such a student perform better even in the trade or profession of his choice.
3. In the light of the social and economic situation prevailing in Nigeria, some children may be required to work in the medium and short term, the work should however be regulated and should not endanger the health and safety of the child. It should also combine protected work activities with some kind of education and social services.
4. A comprehensive study of child labour should be conducted in Nigeria.
5. Vocation schools should be established for children of poor families.

REFERENCES

- Balamir, A (1982) Child Labour Force in Manufacturing Industries in Turkey, *Turkish Journal Of Population Studies* Vol 4: 99 – 117
- Bond, L (1994) AIDS and the Street Children: An Urgent Call to Action. *Boletin De La Oficina Sanitaria Pan Americana* July 117 (1); 84 -8.
- Kulkarni, S (1979) Economic Value of Children; in; Srinivasan K, Sexana P.C. Kanitkar, T. (eds) *Demographic and socio-economic aspects of the child in India*; Bombay, India, Himalaya Publishing Company; 235-52.
- Nigam, S (1994) Street Children on India – a glimpse; *JOURNAL OF Health Management* Jan – Jun 7 (1); 63-7

Okwaraji, F. E, P. O and Akpala C.O (1996) Substance used among Nigerian Street Children, *Ife Psychologia* Vol 4 No 2

Pitt, D. C; Shah, P. M (1983) Child Labour and Health in: Jelliffe, D. B., Jelliffe E. F. (eds) *Advances In International Material And Child Health*; Vol 3; Oxford; Oxford University Press, 1-8

Prisca Egede (Labour Reporter for *Guardian Newspaper* of Thursday April 16, 1998). Report of International Labour Organization (ILO) meeting on "Child Labour in Africa" held in Kampala, Uganda

Remington, F (1993) The Forgotten ones. A Story of Street Children and Schooling in South Asia *Integration* Sept. (37): 40-2.

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INTRODUCTION
We live in an environment that is rapidly changing as a result of technological advancement. Our education is training vainly to cope with the rapid change but unfortunately we have not always been successful in adapting to change due to poor implementation. Teachers are the ones who were all too fixed together in the minds of the learners. A good teacher is expected to impart his subject content and methodology knowledge into a limited professional culture. It is thus advised that pedagogy and content knowledge should be integrated. Science teaching in the present day calls for a shift in paradigm. Emphasis in teaching science have thus shifted from knowing what to teach to knowing how to teach because we are living in a time when scientific knowledge is doubling every 10 to 15 years. Scientific facts change as our understanding of the universe improves. Therefore it is a matter of fact that facts and knowledge which is the present practice of learning with facts, in the paradigm shift, the teacher should now take the pupils to find solutions to problems by using scientific method which is problem oriented in their quest to find a solution to a problem.